

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF INTIMATELY-MIXED HYBRID COMPOSITES

N. J. PARRATT and K. D. POTTER

Perme, Waltham Abbey, Essex, GB

Discontinuous fibres can nowadays be aligned with sufficient accuracy to evaluate a range of hybrid prepregs in which mixing is accomplished at the basic fibre level, rather than as layers or mixed tows of fibre. Increases of flexural strength, damage threshold and residual strength can be obtained by adjusting the knee of the stress-strain curve and the subsequent work of fracture. Prediction of tensile strength has however, proved a difficulty. Constraint effects which increase the observed strain to break of one set of fibres rely on the total load being carried locally by the other set; thus there can be little improvement of overall strength by this mechanism. The microstructural model adopted shows how composition affects strength via the size of clusters of like fibres which occur. A revised lower bound to tensile strength is proposed, assuming each cluster fails at the strength of the weakest member. The bound proves a good fit for the HMS-HTS hybrid and better than the eutectic bound for the HMS-Glass hybrid. This hybrid also demonstrates clearly how strength is augmented by broken fibres of sub-critical length.

1 INTRODUCTION

It will be clear from other papers presented at this conference^{1,2,3} that the technology for producing and applying aligned, discontinuous fibre materials is now at a fairly advanced stage, at least in Western Europe. For the present, these sheet materials are being used for their excellent shaping qualities, and they usually contain a single, well-proven form of carbon fibre. However it is a trivial matter to introduce several different types of fibre, possibly recycled ones, within a single mat, and in this way to improve the balance of properties, including cost. Thus it is important to have a theoretical description to predict where the best mechanical properties will lie, and to discern how they differ from more coarsely-constructed hybrids. We had previously noted that there were no marked discrepancies due to the discontinuous nature of the fibres used,⁴ the tensile strength, stiffness and elastic strain to break of discontinuous laminates being similar to those of conventional laminates, provided the fibres are accurately aligned and of a length at least ten times the critical value. Conclusions for hybrid discontinuous composites may therefore apply where continuous fibres are mixed to the same degree.

Existing bounds to the tensile strength of hybrid compositions are rather broad, due to uncertainties in describing the material behaviour. By considering a microstructural model of intimately-mixed hybrids we first propose an upward revision of the lower strength bound and then show this to be reasonable experimentally. Constraint effects in the observed stress-strain curves are then reviewed, and finally evidence is produced of a hybrid strength contribution from slipping fibres just broken to their critical length. Appropriate composition ranges can then be recognised for ternary hybrids.

2 BOUNDS OF TENSILE STRENGTH IN BINARY HYBRIDS

Although for a system of two fibre types, the Young's modulus of any intermediate composition obeys the straight line rule of mixtures, only when the two sets of elastic fibres have breaking strains which are equal does this rule apply to tensile strength.

The rule also applies to strength in the special case of fibres in which the stress remains constant and is not proportional to strain, due to yielding or pulling out. However, in general if the fibre types do not interact, the tensile strength of the system should follow the well-known eutectic form in Figure 1, characterised by two straight lines PT and TS, depending on whether or not the fibres with a higher strain to break (A) are present in sufficient proportion to accept the load when the first set (B) fails. With sufficiently coarse mixing, but good adhesion, the failure of the first set will produce a significant defect and cause immediate failure of the second⁵ and this represents a lower bound for the system where the two sets interact unfavourably (PTR). Zweben has explored this case.⁶

An upper bound to the strength of the hybrid is determined by the bundle strength of the first set (ND). The load maximum of this set is slightly augmented by the rising load in the second, more extensible set and the failing strain of the first set may also appear slightly enhanced for that reason (DL) after which the broken fragments of the first set may slip and contribute to the total strength of the hybrid (SD). Thus care is required in defining bundle strength.

Figure 2 shows how the relative load carried by a bundle of fibres varies with applied strain, assigning to the mean strength and elastic strain to break of the fibres a value of unity, and coefficient of variation of 15%. Thus the peak of the lower curve describes the strength of a "dry" bundle where each fibre once failed carries no load, whereas the upper curve describes a glued bundle in which every fibre carries half the mean strength after its fracture. Provided that the fibre strength levels considered are those for short gauge lengths, then the latter seems an appropriate approximation to adopt.

The initial positive slope of these curves would of course be proportional to the product of fibre stiffness and volume fraction in a composite. It is therefore

Figure 1 Upper and lower bounds of tensile strength (B fibre less extensible than A).

Figure 2 Concepts of fibre bundle strength (C of $V = 15\%$)

interesting to note from the maximum negative slope that if another set of fibres is present and unbroken, there will be no load maximum observable if the stiffness contribution of the second set is greater than that of the first. What inflection there is will then lie about the average strain to break of the first set.

Now the importance of fine scale mixing of fibres is that it can minimise the size of defects produced. It can in principle suppress or contain the propagation of fracture from one fibre to the next of the same type, enabling that set actually to approach their bundle strength, without creating large enough defects to cause premature failure of the second set. To magnify change, in the experiments described below we have consciously selected an early batch of HMS fibre which has normal strength, but evidently a high level of surface treatment, judged from the brittle fracture of simple HMS-epoxy composites.

For convenience, the familiar terminology of normal distributions is used throughout this work. No extreme value data were available to verify Weibull or Poisson distributions, admittedly a more rational choice, but the properties in question are indeed central ones.

3 REVISED LOWER BOUND

A revised bound for the tensile strength of intimately-mixed hybrids might be to suppose that an enclosed group or bundle of similar fibres will fail in a brittle fashion as soon as the weakest fibre in the group fractures. (This may be initiated somewhat more readily in a discontinuous composite where some additional stress concentration occurs at a fibre end.) Now in a small cluster of fibres, the inclusion of a very weak fibre is an unlikely event and one would not then expect the strength of the cluster to differ very markedly from the bundle strength, whereas it would be a likely event for a large cluster.

Unfortunately, in mixed fibre hybrids, where the fibre sequence is random, the grouping of fibres changes sharply with composition, and at a given composition a range of cluster sizes will be encountered. If it is accepted that with imperfect packing and fibres of equal diameter, a typical fibre is surrounded by five other nearest neighbours, then we can show from the expansion of $(a + b)^5$ the relative probability of that fibre being surrounded by zero to five of its fellows, where a and b are the relative proportions.

TABLE 1 The Weighting Effect of Relative Proportions of A and B on Possible Ways of Surrounding a Single B Fibre with Five Other Fibres

Composi- tion		Isolated	Chain Ends	Single Chain Members	Double Chain Members	Monolithic Blocks	
a	b	(5A)	(4A + B)	(3A + 2B)	(A + 4B)	(A + 4B)	(5B)
1.0	0	1.0	-	-	-	-	-
0.9	0.1	0.59	0.33	0.07	0.01	-	-
0.8	0.2	0.33	0.41	0.20	0.05	0.006	-
0.7	0.3	0.17	0.36	0.31	0.13	0.03	-
0.6	0.4	0.08	0.26	0.35	0.23	0.07	0.01
0.5	0.5	0.03	0.156	0.31	0.31	0.156	0.03
0.4	0.6	0.01	0.07	0.23	0.35	0.26	0.08
0.3	0.7	-	0.03	0.13	0.31	0.36	0.17
0.2	0.8	-	0.006	0.05	0.20	0.41	0.33
0.1	0.9	-	-	0.01	0.07	0.33	0.59
0	1.0	-	-	-	-	-	1.0

Thus one can distinguish from the point of view of crack propagation whether it is an isolated fibre, the end member or part of a chain or double chain of its fellows, or part of a virtually monolithic structure (Table 1). Reference to Figure 3 shows that up to say 20% volume of a given fibre, 75% of that fibre is dispersed either

singly or in clusters (chains) of a few fibres. Beyond 20% by volume through to about 70% by volume, short chain structure predominates, and we assume that it is equally likely that a patch of monolithic material can form a locally thickened part of a terminated chain, as it is that a chain merely links monolithic blocks together. Beyond 80% by volume the termination of a chain is a rare event and it is the other fibre set which is then fully dispersed.

To a first approximation, the proportion of one fibre set which is captive or surrounded by the other set is represented by all but the monolithic blocks. Since each complete chain must have at least two end members, to obtain an indication of number of fibres in a cluster, excluding isolated ones, we divide the proportion of chain ends into twice the sum of chain members and ends taken together (Table 2).

TABLE 2 Typical Cluster Size and hence Weakest Fibre

Composition Relative % in hybrid	Calculated number in chain	Expected strength range of this number (in standard deviations)	Mean Weakest (in SD below mean)
10	2.5	1.45	-0.72
20	3.2	1.8	-0.9
30	4.4	2.2	-1.1
40	6.5	2.65	-1.32
50	9.9	3.07	-1.54
60	18.6	3.7	-1.85
70	31.3	4.15	-2.07
80	85	4.87	-2.43

The question of whether or not a fracture propagates from the first broken fibre in a cluster is governed by the strain concentration produced in neighbouring fibres. This strain concentration is at least 1.2 in the worst case when the load is borne only by nearest neighbours, and this is equivalent for carbon fibres to about one standard deviation of strength distribution. By inspection of Table 2, if at 70% proportion the weakest fibre is say two SD below mean strength, the chances are good of a neighbouring fibre already being one SD below mean, and so fracture can proceed through the cluster in this way. This argument only breaks down, as it should, for very large clusters of fibres. Then it is improbable that a very weak fibre will be surrounded by almost equally weak ones.

To sum up, in the worst case of random but aligned mixing of two fibre types, we have to consider at least four phases of fibre (Fig 4) certainly the extensible A fibres, but with the less extensible B fibres subdivided topologically into a brittle monolithic phase of lower breaking strain, chains having the strength of their weakest member, and isolated B fibres. The relative proportions are shown against composition in Figure 4, together with the predicted strength of the chains, in SD below mean fibre strength, for fibres of equal diameter. To determine which phase will control fracture and to predict hybrid strength, numerical values of average strength and scatter of the B fibres are needed, as well as the strengths and stiffnesses of the monolithic A and B phases.

There are then three fracture modes, two of the same character and predictable from the behaviour of the separate A and B composites, and the third central mode which they may intersect and which depends only on the failure of the chains, and hence on the strength and scatter of the basic B fibres and the relative moduli (m) of A and B fibres. This strength bound is plotted in Fig 5 assuming C of $V = 16\%$, taking the relative proportions from Fig 4. Data for the HMS-HTS system have been inserted in Fig 5 together with the expected dashed bound for that system with $m = 1.57$, and calibrating from a mean fibre strength 1.08% of HMS modulus, and a known modulus⁴ for aligned HMS at 50% vol of 159 GPa.

Figure 3 Effect of composition on distribution of B fibre groups

KEY

- IS - ISOLATED
- CE - CHAIN ENDS
- CM - CHAIN MEMBERS
- MO - MONOLITHIC

Figure 4 Proportions of microstructural phases in binary hybrids

Figure 5 Stress in hybrid at chain failure (C of V = 16%) for different modulus ratios. Proposed bound for HMS-HTS system with data superimposed.

Figure 6 Changes of interlaminar shear strength with composition

The top curve $m = 1$ might apply to recycled carbon fibre blended with new equivalent, if the recycled fibre had become overtreated and embrittled. The lowest curve of Fig 5 is for m infinite, and immediately above it the curve for $m = 5$ (eg glass-HMS).

4 CONSTRAINT EFFECTS

The enhancement of strain to fracture has frequently been demonstrated in matrices of brittle resins, cement, glasses and ceramics, and the effect is most noticeable when the reinforcing fibres are fine and provide an extended surface to which the matrix can adhere. This effect also occurs in hybrids, and theoretical explanations abound.^{7,8,9,10} However, it does appear that it is the propagation rather than the formation of cracks which is being suppressed, and this prompts a cautious approach to fatigue of constrained matrices. Moreover, good adhesion can of course prevent the detection of local, constrained failures during conventional measurements of overall strain.

In hybrids as elsewhere it is necessary to define the tough set of fibres which is to carry load past these "matrix" failures and in our case this will be apparent from the prevailing fracture mode of Fig 5. Because of such constraint one would not expect to see departures from linear stress-strain behaviour in intimately-mixed hybrids until the less-extensible fibres are broken into many fragments. The fact that constrained fibres do break into many fragments and at their normal breaking strain is confirmed by the work of Wadsworth¹¹ who observed individual carbon fibres being strained in a thin epoxy layer, bonded to a massive aluminium plate, and by our own observations below. It appears that constraint will have no influence on overall hybrid strength but a pronounced influence on the stress-strain curve. As previously reported,⁴ although the strain to break in the HMS-HTS hybrids varies with composition from 0.38% to over 1%, only when the strain exceeds 0.8% is a departure from Hooke's law detectable.

5 MATERIALS AND TEST METHODS

The fibres to be used for each composition were first chopped to 3 mm then thoroughly dispersed in the alignment medium by stirring. The fibres used were a highly surface-treated version of high modulus carbon (HMS) and a lower surface treated (HTS) high tensile carbon (both from Courtaulds Ltd). The glass fibre was of type R (from Vetrotex). The aligned felts were manufactured by the normal alignment procedures using a small centrifuge plant, then impregnated with BSL 914, a modified epoxy resin film (manufactured by Ciba-Geigy). The felts were made up at 50% by weight fibre so as to give 50% by volume of fibre at a cured ply thickness of 0.17 mm after autoclave moulding.

The test panels were made in an autoclave using standard bleed and release products. Both vacuum and 0.55 MPa air pressure were applied to the autoclave at room temperature. The heat up rate was set to 2°/min up to 120°C and this temperature was held for 30 minutes. At the end of this time the temperature was raised at the same rate as previously up to the cure temperature of 175°C and the pressure was raised to 0.69 MPa. The cure temperature was held for two hours and then the autoclave was allowed to cool slowly before the panels were withdrawn. Total fibre content in the panels used lay between 48 and 52% except for the 0.6 HMS 0.4 Glass which was 43%. All test data were corrected to 50% by volume in the results reported here.

5.1 Tests

a Flexural strength and Modulus (9 samples/board) The standard testpiece 10 mm wide was used with a 2 mm thick laminate and 40:1 span to depth ratio. The centre loading face was 6.25 mm diameter.

b Interlaminar Shear Strength (8 samples/board) The standard testpiece 10 mm wide was used with a 2 mm thick laminate and 5:1 span to depth ratio.

c Tensile Strength, Modulus and Strain to Break (10 specimens/board) A 1 mm thick 10 mm wide unwaisted tensile specimen was used so as to test the largest volume of material as simply as possible. The specimen was 16 cm long with 4 cm Al alloy plates bonded at each end to spread the gripping loads. These specimens were tested in the wedge grips of a Hounsfield Tensometer set up so that the greatest clamping force on the specimen was at the ends of the Al plates, reducing to zero at the gauge length. The grips ran in a lubricated aluminium trough to ensure accurate parallel motion and reduce extraneous forces as much as possible.

Strain to break was measured with an Instron strain gauge extensometer, held in place with a thin layer of RTV silicone rubber. This arrangement provided enough friction to hold the extensometer in place during tests (the anvils of the extensometer could not grip the specimens by themselves, and in any case could not have been allowed to bite into the specimen). This arrangement also allowed slippage at fracture when a more rigid system could have been smashed. The extensometer proved to be quite robust and was undamaged after many specimens had broken and splintered between its anvils.

d Work of Fracture The specimen was basically that used by Tattersall and Tappin with the notches cut by a 0.2 mm diamond wire saw, but it was 2 mm thick by about 2.5 mm wide and 12 mm long. It was tested in an ILSS rig. Tattersall and Tappin reported a size effect with their samples; about 6% increase in work of fracture being shown for doubling the size of the specimen. However, the convenience of using standard thicknesses of material outweighs any apparent changes in work of fracture due to sample size. Ten samples were used for each composition. The values given are for total energy and must be halved to derive the energy per crack face.

e Residual Tensile Strength after Impact The specimens for this investigation were 12 cm long by 2 cm wide and 1 mm thick of $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$ balanced crossplies with 4 cm long Al plates bonded at each end, giving a 4 cm x 2 cm gauge length. The samples were impacted laterally by drop weight at 0.5, 1 and 1.5 joules (2 samples/impact energy level) and subsequently tested in tension to obtain a residual strength figure.

6 DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The interpretation of strength results for hybrids containing HMS fibres depends critically on the values of strength and standard deviation assumed. The variability of HMS fibre in general and the influence this has on the strength of short lengths 0.5 mm have already been thoroughly investigated.^{14,4} For the fibre batch used here Harris and Dickson¹² have confirmed that the strain to break of 5 mm lengths, the variability and the strength of simple dry bundles of these lengths, were all close to previous estimates. We therefore continue to adopt the previous values for 0.5 mm lengths, ie an average strength of 1.08% of modulus leading to a dry bundle strength of 0.78% of modulus, for a coefficient of variation of 16%. It has also to be noted that when these long fibre bundles were impregnated with CY219 epoxy they indeed failed in a brittle fashion, but with the scatter of results no trend of increased strength with reduced numbers of fibres could be established, though this might seem inescapable.

6.1 The HMS-HTS System

Earlier reported work⁴ has been supplemented with extra data for two intermediate compositions, (Figure 5) and within the scatter of the data, the tensile strengths fit reasonably well the predicted strength transition from completely brittle behaviour to fracture due to failure of separate chains. There is no suggestion that all the HMS fails at a low strain and sheds its load on to whatever HTS fibres are present. In spite of some statistical overlap in breaking strain of HMS and HTS fibre, there is indirect evidence of yielding in compositions 25% HMS 75% HTS, as the HMS phase breaks at the expected strain for virtually isolated fibres. This was detected as a short plateau in a few of the stress-strain curves,

but is perhaps more prominent as an anomalously high flexural strength, and an improved damage threshold, compared with conventional HTS crossplied laminates (Table 3). Such effects might also be induced by uncontrolled changes in interlaminar shear strength, but in this system ILSS was uniformly high throughout (Figure 6).

TABLE 3 Residual Tensile Strength of Crossplied Strips (1 mm total thickness) after Flexural Impact, and Unidirectional Flex Strength

Composition	Unidirectional Flexural Strength GPa	Tensile Strength GPa after impact with:	
		0.5 Joules	0.75 Joules
0.25 HMS 0.75 EHTS	1.27 (6)	0.46 0.47 (99%)	0.044 0.09
0.25 HMS 0.75 HTS	1.42 (6)	0.51 0.53 (105%)	0.12 0.11
EHTS	1.35 (4)	0.42 0.42	0.11 0.11
HTS	1.25 (5)	(72%)	

CV of flex strength and % tensile strength retained given in brackets.

6.2 The HMS-R Glass System

The R glass fibre used has about twice the cross-sectional area of an HMS fibre, but it disperses well and also exhibits a high ILSS in epoxy composites. The tensile strength results are interesting because they show a sharp increase in the load carried by the HMS when the glass is very much in the minority (Figure 7), an effect also noted by Richter.¹³ However, the effect is related here to a much reduced interlaminar shear strength and adhesion in the hybrid (Figure 6). Inspection of fracture surfaces confirmed this. There was an order of magnitude increase in the protruding length of HMS in all the hybrids, with no epoxy resin particles attached, and this was also reflected in the fivefold increase in contribution of HMS to the work of fracture (Figure 8). Although it has yet to be confirmed by a control experiment, in the absence of any obvious physical cause, the results suggest strongly that adhesion to surface-treated carbon is partially at least a chemical effect, impeded in this case by the transfer of coupling agent from glass to carbon, or less likely, the blocking of the most active epoxy groups by the excess of this agent.

Figure 9 shows typical stress-strain curves for hybrid compositions containing 25 and 40% HMS, which both show yielding behaviour as the HMS breaks up. In the 25% composition, although fracture starts very consistently at a strain characteristic of the bundle strength of HMS, the fractured HMS fibres continue to carry load and are broken down to a measured mean length of 0.8 mm, showing that three or four fractures must occur in each fibre to accommodate the breaking strain of 1.9% eventually imposed on the composite.

It is interesting to analyse the stress-strain curve of the 25% HMS hybrid (Figure 9) which consists of an elastic section OA up to 0.75% strain, then fracture of the HMS to its critical length along AB, followed by its steady slippage under constant stress along BC. One would therefore expect BC to lie parallel to OD, the slope corresponding to the glass fibre in the hybrid. In fact it lies parallel to the dashed line from the origin which perhaps corresponds to some fractured blocks of HMS adhering elastically to the glass, making it stiffer, but no stronger,

Figure 7 Tensile Strength of HMS-R glass epoxy system, with eutectic and revised bounds dashed.

Figure 8 Influence of composition and fibre break-up on work of fracture.

Figure 9 Break up of HMS fibre with strain in 40% and 25% HMS-R glass hybrids.

Figure 10 The ternary system carbon-carbon-glass epoxy, with feasible compositions.

and thereby explaining the reduced strain to break of the hybrid compared with the glass. Only a tenth of the HMS appears to be committed in this way, leaving the remaining 90% to impart additional strength. The stress carried by this fibre does appear to be about half the mean fibre strength (see also Figure 7). Thus the strain increment AB in Figure 9 is due to the decreased load in the HMS phase being transferred to the glass phase. Had all the load drained from the HMS phase, AB would extend to touch OD. The mechanism by which the HMS loses load upon fracture could either be through loss of effective modulus (shear lag) or by slippage through the matrix. Since only 10% of the recovered HMS fragments could have an effective modulus less than half the original, and the mean aspect ratio of the fragments is large 100:1, it seems clear that slippage immediately comes into play. Although the tangent modulus of the HMS should be unaffected, the strength of isolated fibres before fracture should be reduced at least 10%, compared with HMS-HTS composites, because of the reduced adhesion and increased critical length of the HMS here.

For the glass hybrids containing 40% HMS, the strain measured in the AB section is very variable, since there is no subsequent strain-hardening, and the glass alone cannot accept all the load after fracture of the HMS. Only a small proportion of this HMS appears to be effective in carrying load once it is broken up, and this is possibly due to the increased number of HMS fibres in a cluster at this composition, on average about thirteen failing together, because more HMS fibres can be packed between these larger glass ones. The hybrid containing 60% HMS exhibits a wide range of cluster sizes (Figure 11) and includes some continuous, monolithic groups, as expected.

In both the HMS-glass and HMS-HTS measurements we also note that only at 25% HMS does the work of fracture contribution prove unusually high (Figure 8). This appears to confirm the composition range in which random break-up of individual HMS fibres can occur, as distinct from consecutive failure of complete small clusters.

Because of the reduced HMS adhesion, one might have expected that the fit of the proposed lower bound might be poor. In Figure 7 a moderate fit is obtained, again considerably more accurate than the eutectic bounds shown. The assumptions here are that all the HMS chains attain the bundle strength, regardless of size, and that with reduced adhesion the monolithic phase is also stronger.

7 CONCLUSION

The strength bounds for hybrid compositions are broad and it is only by identifying the microstructure that the lower bound for intimately-mixed systems can be revised upward. In doing so it becomes clear that the fibres have to be identified not just as two types, but as monolithic phase, dispersed phase and intermingled chain phases, depending on composition. The strength contribution of a cluster of highly surface-treated HMS fibres appears consistent with the strength of the weakest fibre. With reduced fibre-matrix adhesion the strength contribution is less from the dispersed phase, but higher than before from large clusters, and still falls as the content of monolithic HMS rises (>40% HMS). Fibres of the less-extensible group that are dispersed continue to contribute to total hybrid strength after they are broken (<25% HMS) and certainly contribute more markedly to work of fracture in this condition.

Observing these limits, and recognising the ephemeral high strength contribution of glass fibre in humid environments, it is nevertheless feasible to select from Figure 10 ternary hybrids which are stiff, damage tolerant, fatigue-resistant, and still contain some 50% glass by weight.

Acknowledgement

Mr M Jones kindly prepared the hybrid mouldings and test specimens for the experimental studies.

References

- 1 Edwards H E, "A method for the production of high quality aligned short fibre mats". This conference.
- 2 Potter K D, "Deformation mechanisms of fibre reinforcements and their influence on the fabrication of complex structural parts". This conference.
- 3 Richter A, Leis H, "Single fibre and hybrid composites with aligned discontinuous fibres in polymer matrix". This conference.
- 4 Edwards H E et al, Proc ICGM2 AIME, p 976 (1978).
- 5 Chamis C C and Lark R F, "Hybrid and select metal matrix composites", Edit Renton, publ AIAA (1977), p 20.
- 6 Zweben C, J Mat Sci, July 1977, 12 (7), p 1325.
- 7 Aveston J, Cooper G A, Kelly A, "Properties of fibre composites". Proc of NPL Conference (1971).
- 8 Aveston J, Sillwood J M, J Mat Sci, 11, 1877-1883 (1976).
- 9 Bailey J E, J Mat Sci, 13, 195 (1978).
- 10 Bader M G, Manders P W, Proc ICGM2 AIME, p 1147 (1978).
- 11 Wadsworth N J, Spilling I, Br J Appl Phys, 2, 1, 1049 (1968).
- 12 Harris B, Dickson R, University of Bath, private communication.
- 13 Richter A, MBB Ottobrunn, private communication.
- 14 Hitchon J N and Phillips D C, AERE Report 6760, Harwell Jan 1977.

Copyright © HMSO LONDON 1980

Figure 11 Bright clusters of HMS in 60% HMS-40% Glass.